

Mattu University

College of Natural and Computational Science

Department of Mathematics

Lab Manual for Introduction to Mathematical Software.

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Chapter 1

Introduction to LaTeX

What is LATEX?

The history of LATEX begins with a program called TEX. In 1978, a computer scientist by the name of Donald Knuth grew frustrated with the mistakes that his publishers made in typesetting his work. He decided to create a typesetting program that everyone could easily use to typeset documents, particularly those that include formulae, and made it freely available. The result is TEX. Knuth's product is an immensely powerful program, but one that does focus very much on small details. A mathematician and computer scientist by the name of Leslie Lam-port wrote a variant of TEX called LaTeX that focuses on document structure rather than such details.

LATEX is a document preparing system for high-quality typesetting or mark-up language. That means you use symbols and mark-up notations to indicate how you want the document to look, and then some sort of compilation or processing must be used to generate the final document.

L ATEX (variably pronounced as “**La-tech**” or “**Lay-tech**”) is an extremely versatile system for typesetting technical documents.

- ✓ is a computer program for typesetting text and mathematical formulas
- ✓ Uses commands to create mathematical symbols.
- ✓ Not a **WYSIWYG** program. It is a **WYWIWYG** (what you want is what you get) program!
- ✓ The document is written as a source file using a markup language.
- ✓ The final document is obtained by converting the source file (**.tex file**) into a **pdf** file

Why is LATEX?

The following are advantages of using LATEX .

We use LATEX for one or more of the following tasks:

- ❖ Writing journal articles. Most journals require authors to submit manuscripts as **.tex files**.(Article or **amsart** class)
- ❖ Writing a dissertation. (Dissertation class)
- ❖ Preparing slide show presentations for masters, qualifying exam, and professional talks. (Beamer class)

- ❖ Preparing exams, quizzes, worksheets etc. for teaching.(Possibly with exam class)
- ❖ Keep track of sources for an article. (Bibtex)
- ❖ Preparing assignments and papers for classes. (Article or amsart class)
- ❖ Professional typesetting: best output.
- ❖ It is the standard for scientific documents.
- ❖ Processing mathematical (& other) symbols.
- ❖ Knowledgeable and helpful user group.
- ❖ Its **FREE!**
- ❖ Platform independent.
- ❖ Low Sized documents with high quality outputs.
- ❖ Extremely Stable: Handles very large and complex documents smoothly.
- ❖ Cross Referencing capabilities: Figures, Tables, Equations, Index etc.
- ❖ Automatic Numbering: Chapters, sections, figures, equations etc.
- ❖ Automatic generations: List of contents, list of figures, index, bibliography etc.

1.1 Understanding Basics

1.1.1 Command Format in Latex

`\Command Name[optional Argument]{Compulsory Argument}` OR

`\Command Name[optional Argument]{Compulsory Argument}`

Every command in LaTeX is of this form. It starts with Backslash followed by Command Name, Optional Arguments in Square Brackets (if any) and Compulsory Arguments in Curly Brackets (if any).

1.1.2 The Format of the L^AT_EX Document

L^AT_EX input files must conform to a certain structure . They begin with the command `\documentclass`, and all the text of the document must be contained between the commands `\begin{document}` and `\end{document}`.

```
\documentclass[options]{article}
```

```
Preamble
```

```
\begin{document}
```

```
Document text
```

```
\end{document}
```

- The first statement tells LaTeX what kind of document it is to process, as there are different style rules for different kinds of documents. We will use the article document class exclusively in this tutorial. Other possible classes include report, book, and letter.
- The default font size for each class is 10 point. You can use 11 point or 12 point fonts by including this information in the `\documentclass` command as `\documentclass[11pt]{article}` or `\documentclass[12pt]{article}`. You could also use `\documentclass[10pt]{article}`, but since this is the default you don't need to type the [10pt] part.
- The `\documentclass` command must appear at the very beginning of your LaTeX document, before any other LaTeX commands, or you will get an error message.
- The preamble is the section of the file between the `\documentclass{...}` command and the `\begin{document}` command. This is the place to put commands that will influence the style of your entire document and macro definitions that you will use later. You may also load packages that add new features to L^AT_EX. Text is not allowed in the preamble. The `\begin{document}` command indicates the end of the preamble and the beginning of your text . A corresponding `\end{document}` command always ends your files.

1.2 Basic L ATEX structures. (Structure of Latex Document)

Class: Every document has a class. Most tasks are best accomplished in the article class. Other classes that you might have occasion to use are **article**, **report**, **book**, **beamer**, **letter**, **exam**, and **dissertation**. After any initial comments, the first line of every L ATEX file should be a class declaration:

All latex documents have the following structure:

```

\documentclass [... ]{...}
\usepackage {...}

\begin{document}
...
\end{document}

```

1.2.1 Declarations and Environments

Declarations -Are stated once
 -Take effect until further notice

-Can optionally be constrained

Example. `\Document class, \small`

Environments- Have matching begin and end declarations

-Must be constrained

Example. `\begin{document}... \end{document}`

Commands always begin with a backslash **\document class, \usepackage.**

Commands are case sensitive and consist of letters only.

Arguments

Required Arguments -Are contained in curly braces

-Must be included

Curly braces { } after the command name are for **required parameters.**

Example. `\document class {article, report, book, beamer, letter}`

Optional Arguments -Are contained in square brackets

- Can be left out

-Give you more control over the commands

Square brackets [] after the command name are for **optional parameters.**

[options] can be used to set font size (10, 11, or 12 pt), set paper size, use one or two columns, etc.

Example. `\document class [10pt, 11pt, or 12pt] {article}`

Command: \document class

- First line of all L ATEX documents.
- Specifies the type of the document:
article (research paper), report (multi-chapter document), book (for books), beamer (for presentations).

```
\documentclass [options] {
    article
    report
    beamer
    book
    letter
}
```

- Most publishers (**Springer, Elsevier, IEEE, ACM** etc.) have their own document classes. These are **predefined** classes.

1.2.2 Packages

- Packages allow you to further customize L ATEX.
- Packages add new features and commands to **LaTeX.**

- Common packages:
 - amsmath**, **amssymb**: for math symbols.
 - graphicx**: for including graphics and images
- Commands: `\usepackage {package name}`
- `\usepackage{amsmath}`
- `\usepackage{amsfonts}`
- `\usepackage{amssymb}`

```

\usepackage{package}

\documentclass{report}
\usepackage{color}
\usepackage{graphicx}

\begin{document}
...
\end{document}
```

1.3 Font style and paragraphs, and Text formatting

1.3.1 Font type (Style)

1). Font Face

1. **Text weight:** you can also choose text “weight” with “text” commands:

i. `\textbf{boldface}` or `\textbf{Text}`

Example: `\textbf{ Mettu University}`

Mettu University

ii. `\textmd{medium weight}` or `\textmd{Text}`

Example: `\textmd{ Mettu University}`

Mettu University

2. **Text families:** you can also choose text families with “text” commands:

i. `\texttt{Typewriter/teletype family}` or `\texttt{Text}`

Example: `\texttt{ Mettu University }`

Mettu University

ii. `\textrm{Roman family}` or `\textrm{Text}`

Example: `\textrm{ Mettu University }`

Mettu University

iii). `\textsf{Sans serif family}` or `\textsf{Text}`

Example: `\textsf{ Mettu University }`

Mettu University

3. Text shape: you can choose a text “shape” with various “text” commands:

i). `\textsc{small caps text}` or `\textsc{Text}`

Example: `\textsc{ Mattu University }`

METTU UNIVERSITY

ii). `\textit{italics text}` or `\textit{Text}`

Example: `\textit{ Mettu University }`

Mettu University

iii). `\emph{Text},`

Example: `\emph{Mettu University}`

Mettu University

iii) `\textsl{slanted text}` or `\textsl{ Mettu University }`

Mettu University

2). Font Size : You can use the following commands to modify the current font size:

`\tiny`

`\scriptsize`

`\footnotesize`

`\normalsize`

`\Large`

`\LARGE`

`\huge`

`\Huge`

`{\tiny Text}`, `{\scriptsize Text}`, `{\footnotesize Text}`,
`{\small Text}`, `{\normalsize Text}`, `{\large Text}`, `{\Large Text}`, `{\LARGE Text}`, `{\huge Text}`, `{\Huge Text}`

1) `{\tiny Mathematics}`

Mathematics

2). `{\scriptsize Mathematics}`

Mathematics

3). `{\footnotesize Mathematics}`

Mathematics

4). `{\small Mathematics}`

Mathematics

5). `{\normalsize Mathematics}`

Mathematics

6). `{\large Mathematics}`

Mathematics

7). `{\LARGE Mathematics}`

Mathematics

8). `{\huge Mathematics}`

Mathematics

9). `{\Huge Mathematics}`

Mathematics

Alignment

```
\begin{center/flushright/flushleft}  
...  
\end{center/flushright/flushleft}
```

Example

input

```
\begin{center}  
    {\LARGE Mettu University}  
\end{center}  
  
\begin{flushleft}  
{\LARGE Mettu, Oromia, Ethiopia}\\  
{\LARGE 2014 E.C/ 2022 G.C}  
\end{flushright}  
  
\begin{flushright}  
{\LARGE Mettu, Oromia, Ethiopia}\\  
{\LARGE 2014 E.C/ 2022 G.C}  
\end{flushright}
```

Out put

```
                Mettu University  
Mettu, Oromia, Ethiopia  
2014 E.C/ 2022 G.C  
  
                Mettu, Oromia, Ethiopia  
                2014 E.C/ 2022 G.C
```

1.3.2 Paragraphs

To start a new paragraph, either leave a blank line or use the control sequence `\par`. By default, paragraphs are indented by 1.5em, which means 1.5 times the point size of the current font. (1 em is about the width of an “M”.) No extra blank space is inserted between paragraphs. The commands `\parindent` and `\parskip` control paragraph indentation and paragraph separation. To get block paragraphs, for example, include in the preamble the commands:

Paragraphs are separated by a blank line.

You can force a new line using `\\`

To force a new page, use `\newpage` or `\clearpage`

Tex document:

```
\documentclass{report}
\title{Sections and Chapters}
%\author{Overleaf}
%\date{\today}
\begin{document}
    \maketitle
    \tableofcontents
    \chapter{An Introduction to Lua\TeX}
    \section{What is it?and what makes it so different?}
```

Lua\TeX{} is a `\textit{toolkit}`?it contains sophisticated software tools and components with which you can construct (typeset) a wide range of documents. The sub-title of this article also poses two questions about Lua\TeX: What is it?and what makes it so different? The answer to ?What is it?? may seem obvious: ?It?s a \TeX{} typesetting engine!? Indeed it is, but a broader view, and one to which this author subscribes, is that Lua\TeX{} is an extremely versatile \TeX-based document construction and engineering system.

```
\subsection{Explaining Lua\TeX: Where to start?}
```

The goal of this first article on Lua\TeX{} is to offer a context for understanding what this TeX engine provides and why/how its design enables users to build/design/create a wide range of solutions to complex typesetting and design problems?perhaps also offering some degree of ?future proofing?

```
\chapter{Lua\TeX: Background and history}
\section{Introduction}
```

LuaTeX is, in TeX terms, 'the new kid on the block' despite having been in active development for over 10 years.

subsection{LuaTeX: Opening up TeX's 'black box?}

Knuth's original TeX program is the common ancestor of all modern TeX engines in use today and LuaTeX is, in effect, the latest evolutionary step: derived from the pdfTeX program but with the addition of some powerful software components which bring a great deal of extra functionality.

\end{document}

Pdf document:

Sections and Chapters

March 22, 2022

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1.1	What is it?and what makes it so different?	2
1.1.1	Explaining LuaTeX: Where to start?	2
2	LuaTeX: Background and history	3
2.1	Introduction	3
2.1.1	LuaTeX: Opening up TeX's 'black box?'	3

Chapter 1

An Introduction to LuaTeX

1.1 What is it? and what makes it so different?

LuaTeX is a *toolkit*? it contains sophisticated software tools and components with which you can construct (typeset) a wide range of documents. The subtitle of this article also poses two questions about LuaTeX: What is it? and what makes it so different? The answer to ?What is it?? may seem obvious: ?It?s a TeX typesetting engine!?. Indeed it is, but a broader view, and one to which this author subscribes, is that LuaTeX is an extremely versatile TeX-based document construction and engineering system.

1.1.1 Explaining LuaTeX: Where to start?

The goal of this first article on LuaTeX is to offer a context for understanding what this TeX engine provides and why/how its design enables users to build/design/create a wide range of solutions to complex typesetting and design problems?perhaps also offering some degree of ?future proofing?.

Chapter 2

LuaTeX: Background and history

2.1 Introduction

LuaTeX is, in TeX terms, ?the new kid on the block? despite having been in active development for over 10 years.

2.1.1 LuaTeX: Opening up TeX?s ?black box?

Knuth’s original TeX program is the common ancestor of all modern TeX engines in use today and LuaTeX is, in effect, the latest evolutionary step: derived from the pdfTeX program but with the addition of some powerful software components which bring a great deal of extra functionality.

1.4 Tables , figures, Arrays and Lists

1.4.1 Tables

LATEX has two table-related environments: “table” and “tabular”. The floating “table” environment is used to specify location and captioning. The “tabular” environment is used to format the actual table.

Tables are created using the “**table**” environment given below:

```
\begin{table}[t] %% top placement
\begin{tabular}{c|c|c} %% center everything
center & center & center \\ %% doesn't need a \\
\hline
```

```

center & center & center \\
center & center & center \\
\end{tabular}
\end{table}

```

Formal tables and figures will float (change position to fit available space). Use `\caption` and `\label` to caption and label tables and figures.

- You can suggest locations for tables, which are “float”. You can use the following location suggestions, and you may list them in order of your preference:
- **h** – “here”. Try to place the table where at this point in the text.
- **t** – “top”. Try to place the table at the top of the current page; if it doesn’t fit, try to place it at the top of the next page.
- **b** – “bottom”. Try to place the table at the bottom of the current page; if it doesn’t fit, try to place it at the bottom of the next page.
- **p** – “page”. Place the table on a separate page for tables and figures.

Specifying data in the table

Horizontal “data” lines end in “\”.

Column entries are divided by ampersands (“&”).

Horizontal rules can be drawn with “`\hline`”.

l - column is left-justified

c - column is centered

r - column is right-justified

| -draws a vertical

|| - draws two vertical lines together

For example:

Tex document

```

\begin {table}
\centering
\begin {tabular}{|c|c|c|c|} \hline
Method &Groups & Normal & Abnormal & Total \\ \hline
LR & Normal & 40 & 11 & 51 \\ \hline
QR & Abnormal & 17 & 22 & 39 \\ \hline
SR & Normal & \bf{78.4} & 21.6 & 100 \\ \hline

```

```

TR & Abnormal & 43.6 & \bf {56.4} & 100 \\ \hline
\end {tabular}
\caption {Sample Table}
\label {tab1}
\end {table}

```

Pdf document:

Method	Groups	Normal	Abnormal	Total
LR	Normal	40	11	51
QR	Abnormal	17	22	39
SR	Normal	78.4	21.6	100
TR	Abnormal	43.6	56.4	100

Table 1: Sample Table

1.4.2 Figures

L ATEX supports a “figure” environment, where you can place a graphic of some sort (though I think that generally it is best to stick with either encapsulated PostScript R ; however, the “png” format generally works fine also.)

Tables are created using the “**figure**” environment given below:

```

\begin{figure}[PLACEMENT]
\includegraphics[OPTIONS]{FILENAME}
\caption{CAPTION}
\label{LABEL}
\end{figure}

```

Note that the **PLACEMENT** is an option specified with [], not a requirement as with the table environment.

Options

- width = you can specify a width, such as [width=5in]
- height = you can specify a height, such as [height=5in]
- scale = you can specify a scaling factor, such as [scale=0.75]
- angle = you can specify an angle in degrees, such as [angle=45]

Figure example

```

\begin{figure}[h]
\centering
\includegraphics[width=3.2in]{../MaU}

```

```
\caption{\textbf{Mattu University}}
\label{fig:MaU}
\end{figure}
```


1.4.3 Arrays: are environments that have a single argument that specifies the number of columns and the alignment of items within the columns. For each column in the array, there is a single letter in the argument that specifies how items in the column should be positioned: **c** for centered, **l** for flush left, or **r** for flush right. Each row is separated by a `\\` command and items within the rows are separated by a `&` character.

For example

Tex document:

```
\begin{displaymath}
\begin{array}{cclrr}
a_1 & a_2 & a_3 & a_4 & 11 \\
b+2 & c+4 & x_2y^{x+1} & z & 1,000 \\
a+b+c & c & xyz & c - b & 34,500
\end{array}
\end{displaymath}
```

Pdf document

a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	11
$b + 2$	$c + 4$	x_2y^{x+1}	z	$1,000$
$a + b + c$	c	xyz	$c - b$	$34,500$

Matrices

Matrices are by definition numbers or mathematical expressions arranged in rows and columns. The **amsmath** has several environments for producing such arrays.

For example

The system of equations

```
\begin{align*}
```

$$x+y-z = 1$$

$$x-y+z = 1$$

$$x+y+z = 1$$

`\end{align*}`

can be written in matrix terms as

`\begin{equation*}`

`\begin{pmatrix}`

$$1 \quad 1 \quad -1$$

$$1 \quad -1 \quad 1$$

$$1 \quad 1 \quad 1$$

`\end{pmatrix}`

`\begin{pmatrix}`

$$x$$

$$y$$

$$z$$

`\end{pmatrix}`

=

`\begin{pmatrix}`

$$1$$

$$1$$

$$1$$

`\end{pmatrix}`.

`\end{equation*}`

Here, the matrix

`\begin{pmatrix}`

$$1 \quad 1 \quad -1$$

$$1 \quad -1 \quad 1$$

$$1 \quad 1 \quad 1$$

$\end{pmatrix}$ is invertible.

The system of equations

$$x + y - z = 1$$

$$x - y + z = 1$$

$$x + y + z = 1$$

can be written in matrix terms as

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Here, the matrix $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ is invertible.

Note that the environment `pmatrix` can be used within in-text mathematics or in displayed math. Why the `p`? There is indeed an environment `matrix` (without a `p`) but it produces an array *without* the enclosing parentheses (try it). If you want the array to be enclosed within *square brackets*, use **`bmatrix`** instead of **`pmatrix`**.

Example

Some mathematicians write matrices within parentheses as in

```
 $\begin{pmatrix}$ 
```

```
a & b \\
```

```
c & d
```

```
 $\end{pmatrix}$ 
```

while others prefer square brackets as in

```
 $\begin{bmatrix}$ 
```

```
a & b \\
```

```
c & d
```

```
 $\end{bmatrix}$ 
```

output

Some mathematicians write matrices within parentheses as in $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$ while others prefer square brackets as in $\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix}$

There is also a `vmatrix` environment, which is usually used for determinants as in which is obtained from the input

The determinant

```
\begin{vmatrix}
```

```
a & b\\
```

```
c & d
```

```
\end{vmatrix}
```

is defined by

```
\begin{equation*}
```

```
\begin{vmatrix}
```

```
a & b\\
```

```
c & d
```

```
\end{vmatrix}
```

```
=ad -bc
```

```
\end{equation*}
```

The determinant $\begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{vmatrix}$ is defined by

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{vmatrix} = ad - bc$$

There is a variant `Vmatrix` which encloses the array in double lines. Finally, we have a `Bmatrix` environment which produces an array enclosed within braces $\{ \}$.

A row of dots in a matrix can be produced by the command `\hdotsfour`. it should be used with an argument specifying the number of columns to be spanned. For example, to get

A general $m \times n$ matrix is of the form

```
\begin{equation*}
\begin{pmatrix}
a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\
a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\
\hdotsfor{4} \\
a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn}
\end{pmatrix}
\end{equation*}
```

A general $m \times n$ matrix is of the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{pmatrix}$$

Dots

In the above example, we used the command `\dots` to produce a row of three dots. This can be used in other contexts also.

For example,

Consider a finite sequence X_1, X_2, \dots , its sum $X_1 + X_2 + \dots$ and product $X_1 X_2 \dots$.

Gives

Consider a finite sequence X_1, X_2, \dots , its sum $X_1 + X_2 + \dots$ and product $X_1 X_2 \dots$.

Cases

If you understand matrices you should understand the cases environment: syntactically, the cases environment is a matrix that has exactly two rows. A few other commands here require explanation. The command `` adds an invisible `-` to make the spacing come out right. (Try removing `` and see what comes out.) The command `\text{...}` typesets its argument as regular text.

Here's an example of a case-by-case definition.

`\[`

```

|x| =
\begin{cases}
\phantom{-}x,
& \text{\text{if } } x \geq 0, \\
-x, & \text{\text{if } } x < 0.
\end{cases}
\]

```

$$|x| = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x \geq 0, \\ -x, & \text{if } x < 0. \end{cases}$$

1.4.4 Lists

There are three basic kinds:

a). itemized lists (bulleted);

```

\begin{itemize}
\item Sugar \item Banana
\item Chocolate \item Mango
\end{itemize}

```

- Sugar
- Banana
- Chocolate
- Mango

b). enumerated lists (numbered or lettered); and

```

\begin{enumerate}
\item Mix together
\item Boil to 112°C
\item Stir and cool
\item Pour into dish \end{enumerate}

```

1. Mix together
2. Boil to 112°C
3. Stir and cool
4. Pour into dish

c). descriptive lists (topic-and-explanation format).

```
\begin{description}
\item[Fudge] is fun...
\item[Broccoli] sucks...
\item[Exercise] is good
\end{description}
```

Fudge is fun...
 Broccoli sucks...
 Exercise is good

1.5 Mathematical Typesetting, Equations In latex, and Typesetting Theorem.

1.5.1 Typesetting Mathematical Equations

- Latex is extremely good at typesetting math equations.
- Equations are written as text.
- Inline equations (equations within the text) are written between \$ and \$.

Example

Tex document

Assume that \$ \alpha x + \beta y = 1\$, then

Pdf document:

Assume that $\alpha x + \beta y = 1$, then

- Equations on a separate line are enclosed between \[and \].

Tex document

Assume that \$ \alpha x + \beta y = 1\$, then

Pdf document:

Assume that:

$$\alpha x + \beta y = 1,$$

then ...

-Numbered equations are written within the *equation* environment

Tex document:

Assume that

```
\begin{equation} \alpha x + \beta y = 1,
```

```
\end{equation} then
```

Pdf document:

```
Assume that: 
$$\alpha x + \beta y = 1, \tag{1}$$
 then ...
```

To refer a numbered equation, use the command `\eqref`. The equation numbers are updated automatically.

By using Equation `\eqref {eq : my-equation}` , we obtain :

Tex document:

```
\begin{equation} \label {eq : my-equation 2} \alpha x = 1 - \beta y . \end{equation}
```

Pdf document:

```
By using Equation (1), we obtain: 
$$\alpha x = 1 - \beta y. \tag{2}$$

```

Delimiters

These commands `\left` and `\right` enlarge the **delimiter** following them to the size of the enclosed material.

One interesting point about the `\left` and `\right` pair is that, though every **\left** should be matched to a **\right**, the *delimiters* to which they apply need not match. In particular we can produce a single large delimiter produced by **\left** or **\right** by matching it with a matching command followed by a period.

For example,

Tex document

```
\begin{equation*}
\left.
\begin{aligned}
u_x &= v_y \\
u_y &= -v_x
\end{aligned}
\right\} \text{Cauchy-Riemann Equations}
\end{equation*}
```

Pdf document

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_x &= v_y \\ u_y &= -v_x \end{aligned} \right\} \text{Cauchy-Riemann Equations}$$

There are instances where the delimiters produced by `\left` and `\right` are too small or too large.

For example

Tex document

```
\begin{equation*}
(x+y)^2-(x-y)^2=\left((x+y)+(x-y)\right)\left((x+y)-(x-y)\right)=4xy
\end{equation*}
```

Pdf document

$$(x+y)^2 - (x-y)^2 = ((x+y) + (x-y))((x+y) - (x-y)) = 4xy$$

where the parentheses are all of the same size. But it may be better to make the outer ones a little larger to make the nesting visually apparent, as in

This is produced using the commands `\bigr` and `\bigl` before the outer parentheses as shown below:

Tex document

```
\begin{equation*}
```

$(x+y)^2-(x-y)^2=\bigl((x+y)+(x-y)\bigr)\bigl((x+y)-(x-y)\bigr)=4xy$
`\end{equation*}`

Pdf document

$$(x + y)^2 - (x - y)^2 = ((x + y) + (x - y))((x + y) - (x - y)) = 4xy$$

Apart from `\bigl` and `\bigr` there are `\Bigl`, `\biggl` and `\Biggl` commands (and their `r` counterparts) which (in order) produce delimiters of increasing size. (Experiment with them to get a feel for their sizes.) As another example, look at

Tex document

For n -tuples of complex numbers (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and

(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) of complex numbers

`\begin{equation*}`

`\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k y_k|\right)^2 \le`

`\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|\right)\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k|\right)`

`\end{equation*}`

Pdf document

For n -tuples of complex numbers (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) of complex numbers

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k y_k|\right)^2 \leq \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|\right)\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k|\right)$$

For n -tuples of complex numbers (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and

(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) of complex numbers

`\begin{equation*}`

`\biggl(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k y_k|\biggr)^2 \le`

`\biggl(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|\biggr)\biggl(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k|\biggr)`

`\end{equation*}`

For n -tuples of complex numbers (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) of complex numbers

$$\left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k y_k|\right)^2 \leq \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |x_k|^2\right) \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |y_k|^2\right)$$

Here the trouble is that the delimiters produced by `\left` and `\right` are a bit too large.

Affixing symbols—over or under

The commands `\overset` and `\underset` come to the rescue. Thus `\overset{\circ}{a}` produces

a° and `\underset{\circ}{a}` produces a_\circ .

Basic L ATEX provides the commands `\overrightarrow` and `\overleftarrow` also to put (extensible) arrows over symbols, as can be seen from the table. The `amsmath` package also provides the commands `\underrightarrow` and `\underleftarrow` to put (extensible) arrows below mathematical expressions. Speaking of arrows, `amsmath` provides the commands `\xrightarrow` and `\xleftarrow` which produces arrows which can accommodate long texts as superscripts or subscripts.

Thus we can produce

Thus we see that

```
\begin{equation*}
0\xrightarrow{\ } A\xrightarrow{f} B\xrightarrow{g} C\xrightarrow{\ } 0
\end{equation*}
```

is a short exact sequence

Thus we see that

$$0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow{f} B \xrightarrow{g} C \rightarrow 0$$

is a short exact sequence

Note how the *mandatory* arguments of the first and last arrows are left empty to produce arrows with no superscripts. These commands also allow an *optional* argument (to be typed inside *square brackets*), which can be used to produce subscripts. For example
Thus we get

```

\begin{equation*}
0\rightarrow A\rightarrow[\text{monic}]{f}B\rightarrow[\text{epi}]{g}C\rightarrow 0
\end{equation*}

```

gives

Thus we get

$$0 \rightarrow A \xrightarrow[\text{monic}]{f} B \xrightarrow[\text{epi}]{g} C \rightarrow 0$$

Mathematical symbols are also attached as *limits* to such *large operators* as sum (Σ), product (Π), set union (\cup), set intersection (\cap) and so on. The limits are input as subscripts or superscripts, but their *positioning* in the output is different in text and display.

For example, the input

Euler not only proved that the series

$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2}$ converges, but also that

```

\begin{equation*}
\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}
\end{equation*}

```

gives the output

Euler not only proved that the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2}$ converges, but also that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$$

Though the integral symbol in display is larger, the position of the limits in both text and display is on the side as can be seen from the output below

Thus

```

\lim\limits_{x\to\infty}\int_0^x\frac{\sin x}{x}\mathrm{d}x
=\frac{\pi}{2}

```

and so by definition,

```

\begin{equation*}

```

```
\int_0^\infty\frac{\sin x}{x}\mathrm{d}x=\frac{\pi}{2}
```

Thus $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^x \frac{\sin x}{x} dx = \frac{\pi}{2}$ and so by definition,

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{\sin x}{x} dx = \frac{\pi}{2}$$

There is a command `\substack` which will do the trick.

```
\begin{equation*}
p_k(x)=\prod_{\substack{i=1\\i\neq k}}^n
\left(\frac{x-t_i}{t_k-t_i}\right)
\end{equation*}
```

$$p_k(x) = \prod_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq k}}^n \left(\frac{x - t_i}{t_k - t_i} \right)$$

1.5.2 TYPESETTING THEOREM

In Mathematical documents we often have special statements such as *axioms* (which are nothing but the assumptions made) and *theorems* (which are the conclusions obtained, sometimes known by other names like *propositions* or *lemmas*). These are often typeset in different font to distinguish them from surrounding text and given a name and a number for subsequent reference. Such distinguished statements are now increasingly seen in other subjects also. We use the term *theorem-like statements* for all such statements. LATEX provides the declaration `\newtheorem` to define the theorem-like statements needed in a document. This command has two arguments, the first for *the name we assign to the environment* and the second, *the name to be printed with the statement*.

Thus if you want

Example

you first specify
`\newtheorem{thm}{Theorem}` and then type
`\begin{thm}`

The sum of the angles of a triangle is 180° .
`\end{thm}`

Theorem 1. *The sum of the angles of a triangle is 180° .*

Note that in the command `\newtheorem` the first argument can be any name you fancy, instead of the `thm` given here. Also, it is a good idea to keep all your `\newtheorem` commands together in the preamble. The `\newtheorem` command has a couple of optional arguments which control the way the corresponding statement is numbered. For example if you want the above theorem to be numbered 1.1 (the first theorem of the first section) rather than a plain 1, then you must specify

`\newtheorem{thm}{Theorem}[section]` in the `\newtheorem` command.

Then the same input as above for the theorem produces

The other optional argument of the `\newtheorem` command is useful when you have several different types of theorem-like statements (such as lemmas and corollaries) and you want some of them to share the same numbering sequence.

For example if you want Then you must specify

`\newtheorem{cor}{Corollary}`

after the specification `\newtheorem{thm}[section]` and then type

`\begin{thm}`

The sum of the angles of a triangle is 180° .

`\end{thm}`

DESIGNER THEOREMS—THE AMSTHM PACKAGE

The package `amsthm` affords a high level of customization in formatting theorem-like statements. Let us first look at the predefined *styles* available in this package.

Ready made styles

The default style (this is what you get if you do not say anything about the style) is termed plain and it is what we have seen so far—name and number in boldface and body in italic. Then there is the definition style which gives name and number in boldface and body in roman. And finally there is the remark style which gives number and name in italics and body in roman.

For example if you put in the preamble

`\usepackage{amsthm}`

```

\newtheorem{thm}{Theorem}[section]
\theoremstyle{definition}
\newtheorem{dfn}{Definition}[section]
\theoremstyle{remark}
\newtheorem{note}{Note}[section]
\theoremstyle{plain}
\newtheorem{lem}[thm]{Lemma}

```

and then type somewhere in your document

Definition IX.2.1. A triangle is the figure formed by joining each pair of three non collinear points by line segments.

Note IX.2.1. A triangle has three angles. ¹note

Theorem IX.2.1. *The sum of the angles of a triangle is 180°.*

Lemma IX.2.2. *The sum of any two sides of a triangle is greater than or equal to the third.*

We have been talking only about *theorems* so far, but Mathematicians do not live by theorems alone; they need *proofs*. The **amsthm** package contains a predefined proof environment so that the proof of a theorem-like statement can be enclosed within `\begin {proof} ... \end{proof}` commands as shown below:

1.6 BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bibliography is the environment which helps the author to cross-reference one publication from the list of sources at the end of the document. LATEX helps authors to write a well structured bibliography, because this is how L ATEX works—by specifying structure. It is easy to convert the style of bibliography to that of a publisher’s requirement, without touching the code inside the bibliography. We can maintain a bibliographic data base using the program BIBTEX. While preparing the articles, we can extract the needed references in the required style from this data base. harvard and natbib are widely used packages for generating bibliography.

To produce bibliography, we have the environment thebibliography1, which is similar to the enumerate environment. Here we use the command `\bibitem` to separate the entries in the bibliography and use `\cite` to refer to a specific entry from this list in the document. This means that at the place of citation, it will produce number or author-year

code connected with the list of references at the end.

```
\begin{thebibliography}{widest-label}
\bibitem{key1}
\bibitem{key2}
\end{thebibliography}
```

The `\begin{thebibliography}` command requires an argument that indicates the width of the widest label in the bibliography. If you know you would have between 10 and 99 citations, you should start with `\begin{thebibliography}{99}`

You can use any two digit number in the argument, since all numerals are of the same width. If you are using customized labels, put the longest label in argument, for example `\begin{thebibliography}{Long-name}`. Each entry in the environment should start with `\bibitem{key1}`

If the author name is Alex and year 1991, the key can be coded as `ale91` or some such mnemonic string. This key is used to cite the publication within the document text. To cite a publication from the bibliography in the text, use the `\cite` command, which takes with the corresponding key as the argument. However, the argument to `\cite` can also be two or more keys, separated by commas. `\cite{key1}` `\cite{key1,key2}`

In bibliography, numbering of the entries is generated automatically. You may also add a note to your citation, such as page number, chapter number etc. by using an optional argument to the `\cite` command. Whatever text appears in this argument will be placed within square brackets, after the label. `\cite[page~25]{key1}`

See below an example of bibliography and citation.

Tex document:

It is hard to write unstructured and disorganised documents using `\LaTeX`. It is interesting to typeset one equation `\cite[Sec 3.3]{les85}` rather than setting ten pages of running matter `\cite{don89,rondon89}`.

```
\begin{thebibliography}{9}
\bibitem{les85}Leslie Lamport, 1985. \emph{\LaTeX---A Document
Preparation System---User's Guide and Reference Manual},
Addison-Wesley, Reading.
```

\bibitem{don89}Donald E. Knuth, 1989. \emph{Typesetting Concrete Mathematics}, TUGBoat, 10(1):31-36.

\bibitem{rondon89}Ronald L. Graham, Donald E. Knuth, and Ore Patashnik, 1989. \emph{Concrete Mathematics: A Foundation for Computer Science}, Addison-Wesley, Reading.

\end{thebibliography}

Pdf document:

It is hard to write unstructured and disorganised documents using \LaTeX [1]. It is interesting to typeset one equation [1, Sec 3.3] rather than setting ten pages of running matter [2,3].

Bibliography

- [1] Leslie Lamport, 1985. *TeX—A Document Preparation System—User's Guide and Reference Manual*, Addison-Wesley, Reading.
- [2] Donald E. Knuth, 1989. *Typesetting Concrete Mathematics*, TUGBoat, 10(1):31-36.
- [3] Ronald L. Graham, Donald E. Knuth, and Ore Patashnik, 1989. *Concrete Mathematics: A Foundation for Computer Science*, Addison-Wesley, Reading.

1.7 Including Graphics

A figure in a separate PostScript file (*.ps) or Encapsulated PostScript file (*.eps) can be included in a LaTeX document using the graphicx package, i.e., putting `\usepackage{graphics}` to the beginning of the tex file. Thus, if a student starts to draw figures or graphs, the files should be created in the ps or eps forms. Most mathematical or scientific graphics software allows you to export graphics (figures, diagrams, graphs) in ps or eps forms; this includes Mathematica, Maple, Matlab, IDL, and xfig. For instance, in the Matlab figure window, choosing the Export option under File menu, a figure file can be created in the eps format. If a student has some figures created earlier in different file formats, i.e., jpeg, bitmap, etc., they must be converted to ps or eps forms

example

```
\begin{figure}[!htb]
    \centering
    \resizebox{0.8\textwidth}{!}
    {\includegraphics{Capture}}
    %\caption{Inclusion of PDF file}
    \label{Gr: Exam3}
\end{figure}
```


Figure 1: Inclusion of PDF file

1.8 Beamer (Slide)

- ❖ Beamer is a flexible L ATEX class for making slides and presentations.
- ❖ It supports functionality for making PDF slides complete with colors, themes, transitions, overlays, etc.
- ❖ Adds a couple new features to the commands already you know about L ATEX.
- ❖ This presentation was made using the Beamer class

Why using Latex for presentation ?

- Professional slides.
- Processing mathematical (& other) symbols.
- You care about the content and not about how the slides look.
- A lot of templates are available for download.
- Free.
- A lot of help.
- Easy to prepare handouts.

Structure of a latex presentation

All latex presentations using Beamer have the following structure:

```
\documentclass[11pt]{beamer}
  \usetheme{default}
  \usepackage[utf8]{inputenc}
  \usepackage[T1]{fontenc}
  \author{}
  \title{}
  \subtitle{}
  \logo{}
  \institute{}
  \date{}
  \subject{}
  \setbeamercovered{transparent}
  \setbeamertemplate{navigation symbols}{}
  \begin{document}
  \maketitle
  \begin{frame}
  \frametitle{}
  \end{frame}
  \end{document}
```

How to add the title slide?

Example

```
\documentclass{beamer}
\documentclass[xcolor=dvipsnames]{beamer}
\usecolortheme[named=blue]{structure}
\usecolortheme[named=Blue]{structure}
\usepackage{enumerate}
\usepackage{hanging}
\usepackage{ragged2e}
\usepackage{etoolbox}
```

```

\usepackage{lipsum}
\apptocmd{\frame}{}{\justifying}{}
\usepackage{setspace}
\setbeamertemplate{footnote}
\parindent 1em\noindent
\raggedright\setstretch{1}
\hbox to 1.8em{\hfil\insertfootnotemark}\insertfootnotetext\par
\usepackage{graphics}
\usepackage{amsmath}
\usetheme{Madrid}
\usepackage[T1]{fontenc}
\usepackage{geometry}
\usepackage{times}
\usepackage{mathptmx}
\usepackage{txfonts}
\usepackage{setspace}
\onehalfspacing
\begin{document}
\title[Mettu Universty ] {\large\textbf{ INTRODUCTION TO LATEX }}
\begin{figure}
\centering
\includegraphics[width=0.1\linewidth]{MeU}
\end{figure} \author[\textbf{KITILA. W}]{\textbf{By :} \textcolor{blue}{\textbf{KITILA.
W}}} } }
\date{\textbf{\today}}
\maketitle
\end{document}

```


INTRODUCTION TO LATEX

By : KITILA. W

March 25, 2022

KITILA. W. ()

Mettu University

March 25, 2022

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How to add slide?

```
\begin { frame } { T i t l e of your s l i d e }  
t h i s i s an example  
\end { frame }
```

Example

```
\begin { frame }  
  \frametitle { Presentation Outline }  
  \justifying  
  \begin { enumerate }  
    { \large \item \color { black } Introduction }  
    \vskip 0.25cm  
    \begin { itemize }  
      \item \color { blue } Statement of the problem  
      \item Objective of the study  
      \item Significance of the study  
      \item Delimitation of the study  
    \end { itemize }  
  \end { enumerate }  
\end { frame }
```

```

{\large \item\color{black} Review of Related Literature}
{\large \item\color{black} Methodology of the study}
\vskip0.25cm
\begin{itemize}
    \item \color{blue} study period and site
    \item study design
    \item Source of information
    \item Mathematical procedure of the study
\end{itemize}
\item\color{black} Time and Budget Plan
\end{enumerate}
\end{frame}

```

Output

Presentation Outline

- ➊ Introduction
 - Statement of the problem
 - Objective of the study
 - Significance of the study
 - Delimitation of the study
- ➋ Review of Related Literature
- ➌ Methodology of the study
 - study period and site
 - study design
 - Source of information
 - Mathematical procedure of the study
- ➍ Time and Budget Plan

KITLA, W. () Mettu University March 25, 2022 2 / 2

How to add text area ?

Useful if you need to add a definition for example

```
\begin{block}{text}
Write the text definition h e r e .
\end{block}
```

Example

input

```
\begin{frame}{Introduction}
\begin{block}{\centering \textcolor{Green}{\textbf{Background of the study}}}}
\begin{itemize}
\justifying
\vskip0.25cm
\item Integral operators a rise in many branches of mathematics, physics, engineering, biology
and economics, as often a means in modeling real-world situations.
\item The Volterra-type integral operator is one of these class of operators which is introduced
by \textbf{Pommerenke in 1977}.
\item We recall that for a given a space  $H(\mathbb{C})$  of holomorphic functions on
 $\mathbb{C}$ , the Volterra- type integral operator on  $H(\mathbb{C})$  induced by a
holomorphic symbol  $g$  is given by  $V_g(z) = \int_0^z f(w)g'(w)dw$ 
\end{itemize}
\end{block}
\end{frame}
\end{document}
```

Output

Introduction

Background of the study

- Integral operators a rise in many branches of mathematics, physics, engineering, biology and economics, as often a means in modeling real-world situations.
- The Volterra-type integral operator is one of these class of operators which is introduced by **Pommerenke in 1977**.
- We recall that for a given a space $H(\mathbb{C})$ of holomorphic functions on \mathbb{C} , the Volterra- type integral operator on $H(\mathbb{C})$ induced by a holomorphic symbol g is given by

$$V_g f(z) = \int_0^z f(w)g'(w)dw$$

Chapter 2: Introduction to Mathematica

Wolfram Mathematica is a software system with built-in libraries for several areas of technical computing that allow machine learning, statistics, symbolic computation, manipulating matrices, plotting functions and various types of data, implementation of algorithms, creation of user interfaces, and interfacing with programs written in other programming languages. The Wolfram Language is the programming language used in *Mathematica*.

2.1. Getting Started

Mathematica is a powerful computer algebra system (CAS) whose capabilities and features can be overwhelming for new users.

First-Time Users of *Mathematica 9*

Launch the program Mathematica 9 on your computer. Mathematica will automatically create a new Notebook (see typical startup screen below).

Entering and Evaluating Input Commands

Just start typing to input commands (a cell formatted as an input box will be automatically created). For example, type $3+7$. To evaluate this command or any other command(s) contained inside an input box, simultaneously press SHIFT+ENTER, that is, the keys SHIFT and ENTER

at the same time. Be sure your mouse's cursor is positioned inside the input box or else select the input box(es) that you want to evaluate. The kernel application, which does all the computations, will load at the first evaluation. This is a one-time procedure whenever *Mathematica* is launched and may take a few seconds depending on the speed of your computer, so be patient.

Documentation Center (Help Menu)

Mathematica provides an online help menu to answer many of your questions about the program. One can search for a particular command expression in the Documentation Center under this menu or else just position the cursor next to the expression (for example, **Plot**) and select **Find Selected Function** (F1) under the Help menu (see screen shot that follows).

*Mat
hem
atic
a
will*

then display a description of **Plot**, including examples on how to use it (see screen shot below).

2.2. Basic Calculator Operations

Mathematica uses the standard symbols +, -, *, /, ^, ! for addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, raising powers (exponents), and factorials, respectively. Multiplication can also be performed by leaving a blank space between factors. Powers can also be entered by using the palette menu to generate a superscript box (or else press CTRL+6) and fractions can be entered by generating a fraction box (from palette menu or pressing CTRL+ $\frac{\text{ }}{\text{ }}$).

To generate numerical output in decimal form, use the command **N[expr]** or **N[expr,d]**. In most cases, **N[expr]** returns six digits of **expr** by default and may be in the form $n.abcde * 10^m$ (scientific notation), whereas **N[expr,d]** attempts to return d digits of **expr**.

Example

```
In[20]:= Pi
```

```
Out[20]=  $\pi$ 
```

```
In[21]:= N[Pi]
```

```
Out[21]= 3.14159
```

```
In[22]:= N[Pi, 10]
```

```
Out[22]= 3.14159265354
```

2.3. Lists

A list (or string) of elements can be defined in *Mathematica* as `List[e1, e2, ..., en]` or `{e1, e2, ..., en}`. For example, the following command defines $S = \{1, 3, 5, 7, 9\}$ to be the list (set) of the first five odd positive integers.

```
In[2]:= S = List[1, 3, 5, 7, 9]
```

```
Out[2]= {1, 3, 5, 7, 9}
```

To refer to the k th element in a list named **expr**, just evaluate **expr[[k]]**. For example, to refer to the fourth element in S , we evaluate

```
In[3]:= S[[4]]
```

```
Out[3]= 7
```

It is also possible to define nested lists whose elements are themselves lists, called *sublists*. Each sublist contains *subelements*.

For example, the list $T = \{\{1, 3, 5, 7, 9\}, \{2, 4, 6, 8, 10\}\}$ contains two elements, each of which is a list (first five odd and even positive integers).

```
In[4]:= T = {{1, 3, 5, 7, 9}, {2, 4, 6, 8, 10}}
```

```
Out[4]= {{1, 3, 5, 7, 9}, {2, 4, 6, 8, 10}}
```

To refer to the k th subelement in the j th sublist of **expr**, just evaluate **expr[[j,k]]**. For example, to refer to the third subelement in the second sublist of T (or 6), we evaluate

```
In[5]:= T[[2, 3]]
```

```
Out[5]= 6
```

A detailed description of how to manipulate lists (e.g., to append elements to a list or delete elements from a list) can be found in

Mathematica's Documentation Center (under the Help menu). Search for the entry **List**.

2.4. Plotting Graphs

Basic Plot

In this section, we will discuss how to plot graphs of functions using Mathematica and how to utilize its various plot options. We will discuss in detail several options that will be useful in our study of calculus. The basic syntax for plotting the graph of a function $y = f(x)$ with x ranging in value from a to b is `Plot[f, {x, a, b}]`. On the other hand, `Plot[{f1, f2, ..., fN}, {x, a, b}]` plots the graphs of f_1, f_2, \dots, f_N on the same set of axes.

Example

Interactive Graphs

The Manipulate function allows you to change the value of a parameter and to animate your graphics. As an example, we can manipulate the frequency of a sine wave.

3Dploting

2.5. Equation

"Defining Variables" discussed *assignments* such as $x=y$ which set x equal to y . Here we discuss *equations*, which test equality. The equation $x==y$ tests whether x is equal to y .

This tests whether $2+2$ and 4 are equal. The result is the symbol `True`.

Input: `2 + 2 == 4`

Output: `True`

It is very important that you do not confuse $x=y$ with $x==y$. While $x=y$ is an *imperative* statement that actually causes an assignment to be done, $x==y$ merely *tests* whether x and y are equal, and causes no explicit action. If you have used the C programming language, you will recognize that the notation for assignment and testing in *Mathematica* is the same as in C.

Solving Equations

An expression like $x^2 + 2x - 7 == 0$ represents an *equation* in *Mathematica*. You will often need to *solve* equations like this, to find out for what values of x they are true.

Input: `Solve[x^2 + 2x - 7 == 0, x]`

Output: `{{x -> -1 - 2*sqrt(2)}, {x -> -1 + 2*sqrt(2)}}`

2.6. Algebra and Trigonometry

2.6.1. Algebra

You can [factor](#) or [expand](#) algebraic expressions:

(Use `CTRL+6` for typeset exponents.)

```
In[1]:= Factor[x2+2x+1]  
Factor[x2 + 2 x + 1]  
Out[1]= (1+x)2
```

The Wolfram Language uses `==` (two equal signs) to test equality:

```
In[1]:= 2+2==4  
Out[1]= True
```

Combine algebraic expressions with `==` to represent an equation:

```
In[2]:= 1+z==15  
Out[2]= 1+z==15
```

Commands like [Solve](#) find exact solutions to equations:

```
In[1]:= Solve[x2+5x-6==0, x]  
Out[1]= {{x → -6}, {x → 1}}
```

For approximate results, use [NSolve](#):

```
In[2]:= NSolve[7x2+3x-5==0, x]  
Out[2]= {{x → -1.08618}, {x → 0.657611}}
```

Pass in a system of equations as a list:

In[3]:= **Solve**[{x²+5 == y, 7x-5 == y}, {x, y}]

Out[3]= {{x → 2, y → 9}, {x → 5, y → 30}}

Find the roots of an equation:

(|| is the symbol for [Or](#).)

In[1]:= **Roots**[x²+3x-4 == 0, x]

Out[1]= x == -4 || x == 1

If a polynomial is not easily factorable, approximate results may be more useful:

In[2]:= **NRoots**[360+234x-1051x²+11x³+304x⁴-20x⁵ == 0, x]

Out[2]= x == -1.79025 || x == -0.498678 || x == 0.797819 || x == 1.68398 || x == 15.0071

The [Reduce](#) command reduces a set of [inequalities](#) into a simple form:

(Type <= for the ≤ symbol.)

In[1]:= **Reduce**[{0 < x < 2, 1 ≤ x ≤ 4}, x]

Out[1]= 1 ≤ x < 2

The reduced form may include multiple intervals:

In[2]:= **Reduce**[(x-1)(x-2)(x-3)(x-4) > 0, x]

Out[2]= x < 1 || 2 < x < 3 || x > 4

[NumberLinePlot](#) is a handy way to visualize these results:

In[3]:= **NumberLinePlot**[x < 1 || 2 < x < 3 || x > 4, {x, -10, 10}]

Many equations and formulas are available through [natural-language input](#):

In[1]:= **quadratic equation**

Out[1]=

$$x^2 - 2x + 1 = 0$$

$$ax^2 + bx + c = 0$$

x	indeterminate variable
a	quadratic coefficient
b	linear coefficient
c	constant coefficient

$$(x = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a})$$

2.6.2. Trigonometry

For basic trig functions, use standard abbreviations (with the first letter capitalized):

In[1]:= **Sin[x] / Cos[x] == Tan[x]**

Out[1]= **True**

Add “Arc” for the inverses:

In[2]:= **ArcTan[1]**

Out[2]= $\frac{\pi}{4}$

Use **Pi** when working with radian expressions:

(Type `ESCpiESC` for the π character.)

In[1]:= **Sin[π /2]**

Out[1]= 1

Or type `ESCdegESC` for the built-in [Degree](#) symbol:

In[2]:= **Sin[90°]**

Out[2]= 1

Automatically [expand](#) (or [reduce](#)) trig expressions using identities:

In[1]:= **TrigExpand[Sin[2x]]**

Out[1]= $2 \cos[x] \sin[x]$

Factor trig polynomials:

In[2]:= **TrigFactor[Cos[x]^2 - Sin[x]^2]**

Out[2]= $2 \sin\left[\frac{\pi}{4} - x\right] \sin\left[\frac{\pi}{4} + x\right]$

Functions like [Solve](#) work as well:

In[1]:= **Solve[Cos[x]^2 + Sin[x]^2 == x]**

Out[1]= $\{\{x \rightarrow 1\}\}$

Specify a domain for solutions:

In[2]:= **Solve[{Tan[x] == 1, 0 < x < 2 Pi}]**

Out[2]= $\left\{\left\{x \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{4}\right\}, \left\{x \rightarrow \frac{5\pi}{4}\right\}\right\}$

2.7. Differential, Integral, Multivariable Calculus

2.7.1 Differential Equations

The Wolfram Language can find solutions to ordinary, partial and delay differential equations (ODEs, PDEs and DDEs).

[DSolveValue](#) takes a differential equation and returns the general solution:

($C[1]$ stands for a constant of integration.)

```
In[1]:= sol = DSolveValue[y'[x] + y[x] == x, y[x], x]
```

```
Out[1]= -1 + x + e-x C[1]
```

Use [/.](#) to replace the constant:

```
In[2]:= sol /. C[1] → 1
```

```
Out[2]= -1 + e-x + x
```

Or add conditions for a specific solution:

```
In[3]:= DSolveValue[{y'[x] + y[x] == x, y[0] == -1}, y[x], x]
```

```
Out[3]= -1 + x
```

[NDSolveValue](#) finds numerical solutions:

```
In[1]:= NDSolveValue[{y'[x] == Cos[x2], y[0] == 0}, y[x], {x, -5, 5}]
```

```
Out[1]= InterpolatingFunction[ Domain: {{-5., 5.}}  
Output: scalar][x]
```

You can plot this [InterpolatingFunction](#) directly:

```
In[2]:= Plot[%, {x, -5, 5}]
```


To solve systems of differential equations, include all equations and conditions in a list:
 (Note that the line breaks have no effect.)

```
In[1]:= {xsol, ysol} = NDSolveValue[
  {x'[t] == -y[t] - x[t]^2,
   y'[t] == 2 x[t] - y[t]^3,
   x[0] == y[0] == 1},
  {x, y}, {t, 20}]
```

Out[1]=

Visualize the solution as a parametric plot:

```
In[2]:= ParametricPlot[{xsol[t], ysol[t]}, {t, 0, 20}]
```


2.7.2. Integrals

Compute integrals with [Integrate](#):

```
In[1]:= Integrate[8x^4, x]
```

$$\text{Out[1]} = \frac{8x^5}{5}$$

Or type `ESCinttESC` for a fillable mathematical expression:
(For more information on fillable expressions, see [Mathematical Typesetting](#).)

```
In[2]:= ∫ 8x4 dx
```

$$\text{Out[2]} = \frac{8x^5}{5}$$

For definite integrals, type `ESCdinttESC` and specify upper and lower limits:

```
In[1]:= ∫0π Sin[x] dx
```

Out[1]= 2

Use [NIntegrate](#) for a numeric approximation:

```
In[2]:= NIntegrate[x3 Sin[x] + 2 Log[3x]2, {x, 0, Pi}]
```

Out[2]= 28.1531

2.7.3. Multivariate Calculus

[D](#) works for partial derivatives—just specify which variable(s) to differentiate:

```
In[1]:= D[x3z + 2y2x + yz3, y, z]
```

Out[1]= 3z²

Or use the ∂ symbol:

(Type `ESCpdESC` for ∂)

In[2]:= $\partial_{x,y}(x^2 - 2xy + xyz)$

Out[2]= $-2 + z$

Multiple integrals use the same notation as single integrals:

(Type `ESCintESC` for \int and `ESCddESC` for d .)

In[1]:= $\iiint (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) dy dx dz$

Out[1]= $\frac{1}{3}xyz(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)$

Symbolic results can often be quite complicated:

In[2]:= $\int_{-1}^1 \int_{-2}^x (x \sin[y^2] + y \cos[x^2]) dy dx$

Out[2]= $\frac{1}{4} \left(2 \cos[1] + \sqrt{2\pi} \left(-9 \operatorname{FresnelC} \left[\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \right] + \operatorname{FresnelS} \left[\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \right] \right) + 2 \sin[1] \right)$

2.8. Ordinary Differential Equation

An *ordinary differential equation* is an equation that involves an unknown function, its derivatives, and an independent variable.

Differential equations are useful for modeling many physical phenomena some of which are discussed in the next section.

Given a differential equation, our objective is to find all functions that satisfy it. *Mathematica's* command for solving a differential equation is **DSolve[eqn,y[x],x]** where **eqn** is the differential equation to be solved and **y[x]** is the unknown function that depends on the independent variable **x**.

If the differential equation has initial conditions, we use braces `{ }` to group the equation as well as the initial conditions (separated by commas): **DSolve[{eqn,cond1,cond2,...,condn},y[x],x]**, where **cond1, cond2,...,condn** are initial conditions.

Separation of Variables

As discussed in your textbook, there is a special class of first-order differential equations that can be solved by hand using the method of separation of variables. Mathematica can help in applying this method but of course it can solve the differential equation outright. This makes Mathematica useful for verifying solutions obtained by other methods or for solving more complicated differential equations.

Example

Recall that when entering a differential equation in Mathematica, we write $y[x]$ instead of y to make explicit the dependence on x .

Input : `DSolve[{y'[x] == 2(4 - y[x])}, y[x], x]`

Output : `{{y[x] -> 4 + e^{-2x} C[1]}}`

There are four major areas in the study of ordinary differential equations that are of interest in pure and applied science.

Exact solutions, which are closed-form or implicit analytical expressions that satisfy the given problem.

Numerical solutions, which are available for a wider class of problems, but are typically only valid over a limited range of the independent variables.

Qualitative theory, which is concerned with the global properties of solutions and is particularly important in the modern approach to dynamical systems.

Existence and uniqueness theorems, which guarantee that there are solutions with certain desirable properties provided a set of conditions is fulfilled by the differential equation.

Of these four areas, the study of exact solutions has the longest history, dating back to the period just after the discovery of calculus by Sir Isaac Newton and Gottfried Wilhelm von Leibniz. The following table introduces the types of equations that can be solved by `DSolve`.

Linear First-Order Equations

The following is a linear first-order ODE because both $y[x]$ and $y'[x]$ occur in it with power 1 and $y'[x]$ is the highest derivative. Note that the solution contains the imaginary error function `Erfi`.

$$\text{DSolve}[y'[x] + x * y[x] == \text{Exp}[3x], y[x], x]$$

$$\{\{y[x] \rightarrow e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}} C[1] + e^{-\frac{9}{2} \frac{x^2}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \text{Erfi}\left[\frac{3+x}{\sqrt{2}}\right]\}\}$$

Here is the solution for a more general linear first-order ODE. The variables are used as dummy variables for integration. The `Erfi` term in the previous example comes from the integral in the second term of the general solution as follows.

$$\text{sol} = \text{DSolve}[y'[x] + y[x] == Q[x], y[x], x]$$

$$\{y[x] \rightarrow e^{-x}C[1] + e^{-x} \int_1^x e^{K[1]}Q[K[1]] dK[1]\}$$

2.9. Linear Algebra

2.9.1 Matrices & Linear Algebra

The Wolfram Language represents matrices as lists of lists:

```
In[1]:= {{1, 2}, {3, 4}}
```

Enter a table using `CTRL+ENTER` for rows and `CTRL+]` for columns:

```
In[2]:=   a  b
  c  d
```

```
Out[2]= {{a, b}, {c, d}}
```

[MatrixForm](#) displays output as a matrix:

```
In[3]:= MatrixForm[{{a, b}, {c, d}}]
```

```
Out[3]=  $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$ 
```

You can [construct a matrix](#) with iterative functions:

```
In[1]:= Table[x+y, {x, 1, 3}, {y, 0, 2}]
```

```
Out[1]= {{1, 2, 3}, {2, 3, 4}, {3, 4, 5}}
```

Or [import](#) data that represents a matrix:

```
In[2]:= Import["data.csv"]
```

```
Out[2]= {{4, 9, 2}, {3, 5, 7}, {8, 1, 6}}
```

[IdentityMatrix](#), [DiagonalMatrix](#) and others are built-in symbols.

Standard [matrix operations](#) work elementwise:

In[1]:= **{1, 2, 3}{a, b, c}**

Out[1]= **{a, 2 b, 3 c}**

Compute the [dot product](#) of two matrices:

In[2]:= **{{1, 2}, {3, 4}}.{{a, b}, {c, d}}**

Out[2]= **{{a+2 c, b+2 d}, {3 a+4 c, 3 b+4 d}}**

Find the [determinant](#):

In[3]:= **Det[{{a, b}, {c, d}}]**

Out[3]= **-b c + a d**

Get the [inverse](#) of a matrix:

In[4]:= **Inverse[{{1, 1}, {0, 1}}]**

Out[4]= **{{1, -1}, {0, 1}}**

Use [LinearSolve](#) to solve a linear system:

In[1]:= **LinearSolve[{{1, 1}, {0, 1}}, {x, y}]**

Out[1]= **{x-y, y}**

Reference

The Mathematica Documentation Center
<http://reference.wolfram.com>

Chapter:3. Introduction to MATLAB

The purpose of this book is to teach basic programming concepts and skills needed for basic problem solving, all using MATLAB® as the vehicle. MATLAB is a powerful software package that has built-in functions to accomplish a diverse range of tasks, from mathematical operations to three-dimensional imaging. Additionally, MATLAB has a complete set of programming constructs that allows users to customize programs to their own specifications.

MATLAB® is a very powerful software package that has many built-in tools for solving problems and for graphical illustrations. The simplest method for using the MATLAB product is interactively; an expression is entered by the user and MATLAB immediately responds with a result. It is also possible to write programs in MATLAB, which are essentially groups of commands that are executed sequentially.

3.1. Getting into MATLAB

MATLAB is a mathematical and graphical software package; it has numerical, graphical, and programming capabilities. It has built-in functions to do many operations, and there are toolboxes that can be added to augment these functions (e.g., for signal processing). There are versions available for different hardware platforms, and there are both professional and student editions.

When the MATLAB software is started, a window is opened: the main part is the Command Window (see Figure 1.1). In the Command Window, there is a statement that says:

In the Command Window, you should see:

```
>>
```

The >> is called the prompt. In the Student Edition, the prompt appears as:

Figure 1.1 MATLAB Command Window.

Mathematical Operators

MATLAB has two different types of arithmetic operations: matrix arithmetic operations and array arithmetic operations. Matrix arithmetic operations are same as defined in linear algebra. Array operations are executed element by element, both on one-dimensional and multidimensional array.

The matrix operators and array operators are differentiated by the period (.) symbol.

However, as the addition and subtraction operation is same for matrices and arrays, the operator is same for both cases.

```
a = 10;
```

```
b = 20;
```

```
c = a + b
```

```
d = a - b
```

```
e = a * b
```

```
f = a / b
```

```
g = a \ b
```

```
x = 7;
```

```
y = 3;
```

```
z = x ^ y
```

Creating an array

An array is formed by a list of individual elements.

Row Array

For example,

```
>>R=[1, 2, 3, 4, 5]
```

```
R =
```

```
1 2 3 4
```

Column Array

The elements of an array can also be written in the form of a column.

For example, the following statement will create a column array.

```
>>R=[1; 2; 3; 4; 5]
```

Multidimensional Arrays

An array having more than two dimensions is called a multidimensional array in MATLAB.

For example, let's create a two-dimensional array a.

```
a = [7 9 5; 6 1 9; 4 3 2]
```

Vector Operations

Addition and Subtraction of Vectors

You can add or subtract two vectors. Both the operand vectors must be of same type and have same number of elements.

Example : Create a script file with the following code:

```
>>A = [7, 11, 15, 23, 9];
```

```
B = [2, 5, 13, 16, 20];
```

```
C = A + B ;
```

```
D = A - B ;
```

Scalar Multiplication of Vectors

When you multiply a vector by a number, this is called the scalar multiplication. Scalar multiplication produces a new vector of same type with each element of the original vector multiplied by the number.

Example 2.4.2. Create a script file with the following code:—

```
>>v = [12 34 10 8];
```

```
m = 5 * v
```

Transpose of a Vector

On the other hand, a row vector is converted to a column vector using the transpose operator. The transpose operation is denoted by an apostrophe or a single quote (').

```
>> w = v'
```

Matrices

A matrix is two-dimensional rectangular array of real or complex numbers.

Creating a Matrix

Matrix is an array of array. So, it can be generated in several ways. To type a matrix into MATLAB

you must

- . begin with a square bracket, [
- . separate elements in a row with spaces or commas (,)
- . use a semicolon (;) to separate rows
- . end the matrix with another square bracket,].

Example

```
>> A = [1 2 3; 4 5 6; 7 8 9]
```

MATLAB then displays the 3_3 matrix,

3.2. Mathematical functions

MATLAB offers many predefined mathematical functions for technical computing which contains a large set of mathematical functions. Typing `help elfun` and `help specfun` calls up full lists of elementary and special functions respectively. There is a long list of mathematical functions that are built into MATLAB. These functions are called built-ins. Many standard mathematical functions, such as $\sin(x)$; $\cos(x)$; $\tan(x)$; e^x ; $\ln(x)$, are evaluated by the functions `sin`; `cos`; `tan`; `exp`, and `log` respectively in MATLAB.

The **default** in MATLAB is to display numbers that have decimal places with four decimal places, as already shown. The **format** command can be used to specify the output format of expressions. There are many options, including making the format **short** (the default) or **long**. For example, changing the format to **long** will result in 15 decimal places. This will remain in effect until the format is changed back to **short**, as demonstrated with an expression and with the built-in value for **pi**.

```
>> format long
```

```
>> 2 * sin(1.4)
```

```
ans =1.970899459976920
```

```
>> pi
```

```
ans =3.141592653589793
```

```
>> format short
```

```
>> 2 * sin(1.4)
```

```
ans =1.9709
```

```
>> pi
```

```
ans =3.1416
```

MATLAB offers many predefined mathematical functions for technical computing which contains a large set of mathematical functions.

3.3. The Plot Function

Graphics

MATLAB has an excellent set of graphic tools. Plotting a given data set or the results of computation is possible with very few commands. You are highly encouraged to plot mathematical functions and results of analysis as often as possible.

2-D Plotting

The most commonly used graphics display function in MATLAB is the function plot, and the syntax is `plot(x,y)`, where `x` and `y` are two `n`-dimensional arrays i.e. a vector of `x`- coordinates, `x = (x1; : : : ; xn)`, and a vector of `y`-coordinates, `y = (y1; : : : ; yn)`, locate the points `(xi; yi)`, with `i = 1;2; : : : ;n` and then join them by straight lines. By typing `help plot` you can see the various capabilities of this main command for two-dimensional plotting.

The most commonly used graphics display function in MATLAB is the function plot, and the syntax is `plot(x,y)`, where `x` and `y` are two `n`-dimensional arrays.

SYMBOL	COLOR	SYMBOL	LINE STYLE	SYMBOL	MARKER
<code>k</code>	Black	<code>-</code>	Solid	<code>+</code>	Plus sign
<code>r</code>	Red	<code>--</code>	Dashed	<code>o</code>	Circle
<code>b</code>	Blue	<code>:</code>	Dotted	<code>*</code>	Asterisk
<code>g</code>	Green	<code>-.</code>	Dash-dot	<code>.</code>	Point
<code>c</code>	Cyan	<code>none</code>	No line	<code>×</code>	Cross
<code>m</code>	Magenta			<code>s</code>	Square
<code>y</code>	Yellow			<code>d</code>	Diamond

Example: 1

```
% This script plots sin(x) and cos(x) in the same Figure
```

```
% Window for values of x ranging from 0 to 2*pi
```

```
clf
```

```
x = 0: 2*pi/40: 2*pi;
```

```
y = sin(x);
```

```
plot(x,y,'ro')
```

```
hold on
```

```
y = cos(x);
```

```
plot(x,y,'b+')
```

```
legend('sin', 'cos')
```

```
title('sin and cos on one graph')
```



```
x=-pi:pi/1000:3*pi;
```

```
y=sin(x);
```

```
z=cos(x);
```

```
plot(x,y,x,z);xlabel('x'),ylabel('y'),legend('sin(x)','cos(x)')
```


Create x as 100 linearly spaced values between -2π and 2π .

```
x=linspace(-2*pi,2*pi,100);
```

```
y1=sin(x);
```

```
y2=cos(x);
```

```
figure
```

```
plot(x,y1,x,y2),title('Line plot of sine and cosine between  $-2\pi$  and  $2\pi$ '),xlabel('  $-2\pi \leq x \leq 2\pi$  '),legend({'y1=sin(x)', 'y2=cos(x)'}, 'Location','southwest');
```

```
set(gca,'FontSize',15)
```



```
x = [-6:0.01:6];
```

```
y = tanh(x);
```

```
plot(x,y),grid on
```



```
x = [0:0.01:2];
y = sinh(x);
z = cosh(x);
plot(x,y,x,z,'-','LineWidth',3),xlabel('x'),ylabel('Potential'),legend('sinh(x)','cosh(x)')
```


Coloring

```
x = [-5:0.01:5];
y = sinh(x);
z = cosh(x);
```

```
plot(x,y,'r',x,z,'b--')
```



```
x = 0:pi/100:2*pi;  
y1 = 2*cos(x);  
y2 = cos(x);  
y3 = 0.5*cos(x);  
plot(x,y1,'--',x,y2,'-',x,y3,':')  
xlabel('0 \leq x \leq 2\pi')  
ylabel('Cosine functions')  
legend('2*cos(x)', 'cos(x)', '0.5*cos(x)')  
title('Typical example of multiple plots')  
axis([0 2*pi -3 3])
```


3-D Plotting

MATLAB has a variety of functions for displaying and visualizing data in 3-D, either as lines in 3-D, or as various types of surfaces. Three-dimensional plots basically display a surface defined by a function in two variables, $g = f(x; y)$. As before, to define g , we first create a set of (x,y) points over the domain of the function using the `meshgrid` command.

```
clear all
```

```
close all
```

```
[x,y]=meshgrid([-2:.2:2]);
```

```
z=x.*exp(-x.^2-y.^2);
```

```
figure
```

```
surf(x,y,z,gradient(z))
```

```
colorbar
```


Line Plots of 3-D Data

The 3-D analog of the plot function is plot3. If x, y, and z are three vectors of the same length,

```
>>plot3(x,y,z)
```

generates a line in 3-D through the points whose coordinates are the elements of x, y, and z and then produces a 2-D projection of that line on the screen. For example, these statements produce a helix.

```
>>t = 0:pi/50:10*pi;
```

```
>>plot3(sin(t),cos(t),t)
```

```
>>axis square; grid on
```

MATLAB generates the following graph:

3.4 Control structure

3.4.1 Loop Control Statements

Within any program, you can define sections of code that either repeat in a loop or conditionally execute. Loops use a **for** or **while** keyword, and conditional statements use **if** or **switch**.

Additional keywords provide finer control over the program flow.

With loop control statements, you can repeatedly execute a block of code. There are two types of loops:

- **for** statements loop a specific number of times, and keep track of each iteration with an incrementing index variable.

For example, preallocate a 10-element vector, and calculate five values:

```
x = ones(1,10);
for n = 2:6
    x(n) = 2 * x(n - 1);
end
```

- **while** statements loop as long as a condition remains true.

For example, find the first integer n for which `factorial(n)` is a 100-digit number:

```
n = 1;
nFactorial = 1;
while nFactorial < 1e100
    n = n + 1;
    nFactorial = nFactorial * n;
end
```

Each loop requires the `end` keyword.

It is a good idea to indent the loops for readability, especially when they are nested (that is, when one loop contains another loop):

```
A = zeros(5,100);
for m = 1:5
    for n = 1:100
        A(m, n) = 1/(m + n - 1);
    end
end
```

You can programmatically exit a loop using a **break** statement, or skip to the next iteration of a loop using a **continue** statement. For example, count the number of lines in the help for the `magic` function (that is, all comment lines until a blank line):

```
fid = fopen('magic.m','r');
count = 0;
while ~feof(fid)
```

```

    line = fgetl(fid);
    if isempty(line)
        break
    elseif ~strncmp(line,'% ',1)
        continue
    end
    count = count + 1;
end
fprintf('%d lines in MAGIC help\n',count);
fclose(fid);

```

Display the multiples of 7 from 1 through 50. If a number is not divisible by 7, use `continue` to skip the `disp` statement and pass control to the next iteration of the `for` loop.

```

for n = 1:50
    if mod(n,7)
        continue
    end
    disp(['Divisible by 7: ' num2str(n)])
end

```

```

Divisible by 7: 7
Divisible by 7: 14
Divisible by 7: 21
Divisible by 7: 28
Divisible by 7: 35
Divisible by 7: 42
Divisible by 7: 49

```

5.5. Matrix Computations

As we have already seen, a *matrix* can be thought of as a table of values in which there are both rows and columns. The general form of a matrix A (which is sometimes written as $[A]$) is shown here:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix} = a_{ij} \quad i = 1, \dots, m; \quad j = 1, \dots, n$$

This matrix has m rows and n columns, so the size is $m \times n$. A vector is a special case of a matrix, in which one of the dimensions (either m or n) is 1. A row vector is a $1 \times n$ matrix. A column vector is an $m \times 1$ matrix. A scalar is a special case of a matrix in which both m and n are 1, so it is a single value or a 1×1 matrix.

Example

Here's an example of performing these substitutions using MATLAB:

```
>> a = [1 3 0; 2 1 3; 4 2 3]
```

```
a =
```

```
1 3 0
2 1 3
4 2 3
```

```
>> b = [1 6 3]
```

```
b =
```

```
1
6
3
```

```
>> ab = [a b]
```

```
ab =
```

```
1 3 0 1
2 1 3 6
4 2 3 3
```

```
>> ab(2,:) = ab(2,:) - 2*ab(1,:)
```

```
ab =
```

```
1 3 0 1
0 -5 3 4
```

```

4 2 3 3
>> a=[4 3 2; 1 5 3; 1 2 3]
a =
4 3 2
1 5 3
1 2 3
>> inv(a)
ans =
0.3000    -0.1667    -0.0333
0         0.3333    -0.3333
-0.1000   -0.1667     0.5667
A = [5 -3 2; -3 8 4; 2 4 -9];
B = [10; 20; 9;];
X = A\B
X =
3.4442
3.1982
1.1868

```

Determinant of a Matrix

Determinant of a matrix is calculated using the det function of MATLAB. Determinant of a matrix

A is given by det(A).

Example .Create a script file and type the following code:

```

>>A = [ 1 2 3; 2 3 4; 1 2 5]
>>det(A)

```

When you run the file, it displays the following result:

```

A =
1 2 3
2 3 4
1 2 5
ans = -2

```

Transpose of a Matrix

The transpose operation switches the rows and columns in a matrix, that is, flips a matrix about its main diagonal and it turns a row vector into a column vector. The transpose operation is denoted by an apostrophe or a single quote (').

Example. Create a script file with the following code:

```
>>A = [10 12 13; 14 8 6; 27 7 9]
>>B = A'
```

When you run the file, it displays the following result:

```
A =
    10    12    13
    14     8     6
    27     7     9
```

```
B =
    10    14    27
    12     8     7
    13     6     9
```

Matrix Multiplication

Consider two matrices A and B. If A is an $m \times n$ matrix and B is an $n \times p$ matrix, they could be multiplied together to produce an $m \times p$ matrix C. Matrix multiplication is possible only if the number of columns n in A is equal to the number of rows n in B.

In matrix multiplication, the elements of the rows in the first matrix are multiplied with corresponding columns in the second matrix. Each element in the $(i; j)^{\text{th}}$ position, in the resulting matrix C, is the summation of the products of elements in i^{th} row of first matrix with the corresponding element in the j^{th} column of the second matrix.

Example. Create a script file with the following code:

```
>>A = [ 1 2 3; 2 3 4; 1 2 5]
>>B = [ 2 1 3; 5 0 -2; 2 3 -1]
>>prod(A*B) =
```

When you run the file, it displays the following result:

```
A =
```

```

1     2     3
2     3     4
1     2     5
B =
     2     1     3
     5     0    -2
     2     3    -1
ans =
    18    10    -4
    27    14    -4
    22    16    -6

```

3.6. Symbolic Mathematics

Symbolic mathematics means doing mathematics on symbols (not numbers!). For example, $a + a$ is $2a$. The symbolic math functions are in the Symbolic Math Toolbox in MATLAB. Toolboxes contain related functions and are add-ons to MATLAB.

To find out about the symbolic functions, help can be used: *help toolbox\symbolic*.

Symbolic Variables and Expressions MATLAB has a type called `sym` for symbolic variables and expressions; these work with strings. For example, to create a symbolic variable `a` and perform the addition just described, first a symbolic variable would be created by passing the string 'a' to the `sym` function:

Example

```

>> a = sym('a');
>> a+a
ans =2*a

```

Chapter 4. Python (programming language) Overview

Python is a high-level, general-purpose programming language. Its design philosophy emphasizes code readability with the use of significant indentation. Its language constructs and object-oriented approach aim to help programmers write clear, logical code for small- and large-scale projects.

- Python was built to be easier to use than other programming languages. It's usually much easier to read Python code and much faster to write code in Python than in other languages.
- Python is an easy to learn, powerful programming language. It has efficient high-level data structures and a simple but effective approach to object-oriented programming.
- Python's **elegant syntax and dynamic typing, together with its interpreted nature**, make it an ideal language for **scripting and rapid application development in many** areas on most platforms.

What can Python do?

- Python can be used on a server to create web applications.
- Python can be used alongside software to create workflows.
- Python can connect to database systems. It can also read and modify files.
- Python can be used to handle big data and perform complex mathematics.
- Python can be used for rapid prototyping, or for production-ready software development.

Why Python?

- Python works on different platforms (Windows, Mac, Linux, Raspberry Pi, etc).
- Python has a simple syntax similar to the English language.
- Python has syntax that allows developers to write programs with fewer lines than some other programming languages.
- Python can be treated in a procedural way, an object-oriented way or a functional way.

4.2. Working with Python

Open Jupyter Notebook

Jupyter gives the look of presenting the flow of code to any laymen people or business or any higher management for better visualization.

Open a New Python Notebook

4.3. Variables and Data Types

4.3.1. Variables

Variables are containers for storing data values.

A variable lets you store a value by assigning it to a name. The name can be used to refer to the value later in the program.

For example, in game development, you would use a variable to store the points of the player.

What's the point of playing if you don't know who's winning right!

Creating Variables

Python has no command for declaring a variable.

A variable is created the moment you first assign a value to it.

To assign a variable, use one equals sign

```
user = "James"
```

Example

```
x = 5  
y = "John"  
print(x)  
print(y)
```

Output

```
5  
John
```

Variable Names

Naming your variables is pretty flexible. You can use **letters**, **numbers**, and **under scores** in variable names. But you **can't** use special symbols, or start the name with a number.

Don't forget, Python is a case sensitive language. Which means, **Last name** and **last name** are two different variable names.

Which of these is a valid variable name in Python?

- A_VARIABLE_NAME
- a-variable%name
- 123

4.3.2. Built-in Data Types

In programming, data type is an important concept.

Variables can store data of different types, and different types can do different things.

Python has the following data types built-in by default, in these categories:

Text Type: `str`

Numeric Types: `int, float, complex`

Sequence Types: `list, tuple, range`

Mapping Type: `dict`

Set Types: `set, frozenset`

Boolean Type: `bool`

Binary Types: `bytes, bytearray, memoryview`

Python Data Types –int, float, complex

Program

```
a = 5

print(a, "is of type", type(a))

a = 2.0

print(a, "is of type", type(a))

a = 1+2j

•print(a, "is complex number?", is instance(1+2j,complex))
```

```
OUTPUT
5 is of type <class 'int'>
2.0 is of type <class 'float'>
(1+2j) is complex number? True
```

4.4. Control Structures

4.4.1. Control Statement -break

Infinite loops may sound cool, but they're not always useful.

To end a **while** loop prematurely, we can use a **break** statement.

For example, we can break an infinite loop if some condition is met:

```
i= 0
while True:
    print(i)
    i= i+ 1
    if i>= 5:
        print("Breaking")
        break
print("Finished")
```

•**An example use case of break:** An infinite while loop can be used to continuously take user input. For example, you are making a calculator and need to take numbers from the user to add and stop, when the user enters "**stop**". In this case, the **break** statement can be used to end the infinite loop when the user input equals "stop".

•Using the **break** statement outside of a loop causes an error.

4.4.2. Control Statement -Continue

•Unlike **break**, **continue** jumps back to the top of the loop, rather than stopping it. Basically, the **continue** statement stops the current iteration and continues with the next one.

For example:

```
i= 1
while i<=10:
    print(i)
    i+=1
    if i==5:
        print("missing 3")
        continue
```

4.5. Repetitive Structure

4.5.1. Looping Statement / Iterative Statement

The for loop in Python is **used to iterate over a sequence/iterator (list,tuple,string) or other iterable objects**. Iterating over a sequence is called traversal.

•Syntax of for Loop

for <val> in <sequence/iterator>:

Body of for loop

- ✓ Here, val is the variable that takes the value of the item inside the sequence on each iteration.
- ✓ Loop continues until we reach the last item in the sequence. The body of for loop is separated from the rest of the code using indentation

Program 1

```
str="Welcome"
```

```
for i in str:
```

```
    print(i)
```

Program 2

```
fruits = ["apple", "banana", "cherry"]#list
```

```
for x in fruits:
```

```
    print(x)
```

OUTPUT 1

```
W
e
l
c
o
m
e
```

OUTPUT 2

```
Apple
Banana
cherry
```

The range() Function

To loop through a set of code a specified number of times, we can use the `range()` function,

The `range()` function returns a sequence of numbers, starting from 0 by default, and increments by 1 (by default), and ends at a specified number.

Example

Using the `range()` function:

```
for x in range(5):  
    print(x)
```

Note that `range(6)` is not the values of 0 to 6, but the values 0 to 5.

OUTPUT
0
1
2
3
4

The `range()` function defaults to 0 as a starting value, however it is possible to specify the starting value by adding a parameter: `range(2, 6)`, which means values from 2 to 6 (but not including 6):

Example

Using the start parameter:

```
for x in range(2, 6):  
    print(x)
```

The `range()` function defaults to increment the sequence by 1, however it is possible to specify the increment value by adding a third parameter: `range(2, 30, 3)`

Example

Increment the sequence with 3 (default is 1):

```
for x in range(1, 10, 3):  
    print(x)
```

OUTPUT
1
4
7

While loop

•A **while** loop statement in Python programming language repeatedly executes a target statement as long as a given condition is true.

while expression:

statement(s)

For example

```
x = 1
while x < 10:
    if x%2 == 0:
        print(str(x) + " is even")
    else:
        print(str(x) + " is odd")
    x += 1
```

4.6. User Defined Functions

•A function that you define yourself in a program is known as user defined function.

•You can give any name to a user defined function.

•SYNTAX:

```
def function_name([parameter_1, parameter_2, ...]) :
statements
....
return <[value1,value2]>
```

Example 1: Function without argument and without return type

```
def my_function():  
    print("Hello from a function")  
  
my_function()
```

OUTPUT

Hello from a function

•Example 2: Function with argument and without return type

```
def sum(a,b):  
    total = a + b  
    print("The sum of",a,"and",b,"is:",total)  
  
x = int(input("Enter First Number: "))  
y = int(input("Enter Second Number: "))  
sum(x,y)
```

OUTPUT

```
Enter First Number: 10  
Enter Second Number: 20  
The sum of 10 and 20 is: 30
```

Example 3: Function with argument and with return type

```
def sum(a,b):  
    total = a + b  
    return total  
  
x = int(input("Enter First Number: "))  
y = int(input("Enter Second Number: "))  
z=sum(x, y)  
print("The sum of",x,"and",y,"is:",z)
```

OUTPUT

```
Enter First Number: 10  
Enter Second Number: 20  
The sum of 10 and 20 is: 30
```

4.7. Strings

Strings in python are surrounded by either single quotation marks, or double quotation marks.

'hello' is the same as "hello".

You can display a string literal with the `print()` function:

Example

```
print("Hello")  
print('Hello')
```

Output: Hello

Assign String to a Variable

Assigning a string to a variable is done with the variable name followed by an equal sign and the string:

Example

```
a = "Hello"  
print(a)
```

Output: Hello

Slicing Strings

Slicing

You can return a range of characters by using the slice syntax.

Specify the start index and the end index, separated by a colon, to return a part of the string.

Example

Get the characters from position 2 to position 5 (not included):

```
b = "Hello, World!"  
print(b[2:5])
```


Output: llo

String Concatenation

To concatenate, or combine, two strings you can use the + operator.

Example

Merge variable a with variable b into variable c:

```
a = "Hello"  
b = "World"  
c = a + b  
print(c)
```

```
Output: HelloWorld
```

4.8. Python Lists

Lists are used to store multiple items in a single variable.

Lists are created using square brackets:

Example

Create a List:

```
thislist = ["apple", "banana", "cherry"]  
print(thislist)
```

List Items

List items are ordered, changeable, and allow duplicate values.

List items are indexed, the first item has index `[0]`, the second item has index `[1]` etc.

Ordered

When we say that lists are ordered, it means that the items have a defined order, and that order will not change.

If you add new items to a list, the new items will be placed at the end of the list.

Changeable

The list is changeable, meaning that we can change, add, and remove items in a list after it has been created.

Allow Duplicates

Since lists are indexed, lists can have items with the same value:

Example

Lists allow duplicate values:

```
thislist = ["apple", "banana", "cherry", "apple", "cherry"]  
print(thislist)
```

List Length

To determine how many items a list has, use the `len()` function:

Example

Print the number of items in the list:

```
thislist = ["apple", "banana", "cherry"]  
print(len(thislist))
```

Access List Items

List items are indexed and you can access them by referring to the index number:

Example

Print the second item of the list:

```
thislist = ["apple", "banana", "cherry"]  
print(thislist[1])
```

Change Item Value

To change the value of a specific item, refer to the index number:

Example

Change the second item:

```
thislist = ["apple", "banana", "cherry"]  
thislist[1] = "blackcurrant"  
print(thislist)
```

Add List Items

To add an item to the end of the list, use the `append()` method:

Example

Using the `append()` method to append an item:

```
thislist = ["apple", "banana", "cherry"]
thislist.append("orange")
print(thislist)
```

Remove List Items

The `remove()` method removes the specified item.

Example

Remove "banana":

```
thislist = ["apple", "banana", "cherry"]
thislist.remove("banana")
print(thislist)
```

Remove Specified Index

The `pop()` method removes the specified index.

Example

Remove the second item:

```
thislist = ["apple", "banana", "cherry"]
thislist.pop(1)
print(thislist)
```

4.9. Input / Output Statements

- `input()` and `print()` are widely used for standard input and output operations respectively
- We use the `print()` function to output data to the standard output device (screen)

Example

```
print('Welcome')
```

output : Welcome

```
x=10
```

```
print(x)
```

output: 10

```
x=10
```

```
print("The value of the variable x is", x)
```

output : The value of the variable x is 10

Input Statement

The syntax for input() is:

```
input([prompt])
```

where prompt is the string we wish to display on the screen. It is optional.

- The return type of input statement is always a String

Example

```
num=input('Enter a Number: ')
```

```
print("The value Entered is",num)
```

OUTPUT

```
Enter a Number: 10.5
```

```
The value Entered is 10.5
```

- Check the type of the variable, Do you think the type will be float since the value given is 10.5?
- But the type is strongly

PROGRAM

```
num=input('Enter a Number')
```

```
print("The value Entered is",num)
```

```
print(type(num))
```

OUTPUT

```
Enter a Number10.5
```

```
The value Entered is 10.5
```

```
<class 'str'>
```

- ✓ We have to convert the type of num to the proper data type float using the function float() so that we can do some arithmetic operations on num.

PROGRAM

```
num=float(input('Enter a Number'))
```

```
print("The value Entered is",num)
```

```
print(type(num))
```

OUTPUT

```
Enter a Number10.5
```

```
The value Entered is 10.5
```

```
<class 'float'>
```

4.10. Python Dictionaries

Dictionaries are used to store data values in key:value pairs.

A dictionary is a collection which is ordered*, changeable and does not allow duplicates.

As of Python version 3.7, dictionaries are *ordered*. In Python 3.6 and earlier, dictionaries are *unordered*.

Dictionaries are written with curly brackets, and have keys and values:

Example

Create and print a dictionary:

```
thisdict = {  
    "brand": "Ford",  
    "model": "Mustang",  
    "year": 1964  
}  
print(thisdict)
```

output: `{'brand': 'Ford', 'model': 'Mustang', 'year': 1964}`

Dictionary Items

Dictionary items are ordered, changeable, and does not allow duplicates.

Dictionary items are presented in key:value pairs, and can be referred to by using the key name.

Example

Print the "brand" value of the dictionary:

```
thisdict = {  
    "brand": "Ford",  
    "model": "Mustang",  
    "year": 1964
```

```
}  
print(thisdict["brand"])  
    type()
```

From Python's perspective, dictionaries are defined as objects with the data type 'dict':

```
<class 'dict'>
```

4.11. Object-Oriented Programming (OOP) in Python

What is object-oriented

OOP can be defined as a pattern that uses “Objects” to do everything (or) anything, whoever requests for.

Object-oriented programming (OOP) is a method of structuring a program by bundling related properties and behaviors into individual **objects**. In this tutorial, you’ll learn the basics of object-oriented programming in Python.

Conceptually, objects are like the components of a system. Think of a program as a factory assembly line of sorts. At each step of the assembly line a system component processes some material, ultimately transforming raw material into a finished product.

An object contains data, like the raw or preprocessed materials at each step on an assembly line, and behavior, like the action each assembly line component performs.

Python is an object oriented programming language.

Almost everything in Python is an object, with its properties and methods.

A Class is like an object constructor, or a "blueprint" for creating objects.

Everything is objects!

Create a class, which is like a blueprint for creating an object

Use classes to create new objects

Model systems with class inheritance

School, Bicycle & Pen are objects

Objects are real-world entity

Objects have state& behavior

Create a Class

To create a class, use the keyword `class`:

```
class MyClass:
```

```
    x = 5
```

```
print(MyClass)
```

Create Object

Now we can use the class named MyClass to create objects:

Example

Create a class named MyClass, with a property named x:

```
class MyClass:
```

```
    x = 5
```

```
p1 = MyClass()
```

```
print(p1.x)
```

The `__init__()` Function

The examples above are classes and objects in their simplest form, and are not really useful in real life applications.

To understand the meaning of classes we have to understand the built-in `__init__()` function.

All classes have a function called `__init__()`, which is always executed when the class is being initiated.

Use the `__init__()` function to assign values to object properties, or other operations that are necessary to do when the object is being created:

Example

Create a class named `Person`, use the `__init__()` function to assign values for name and age:

```
class Person:
    def __init__(self, name, age):
        self.name = name
        self.age = age
```

```
p1 = Person("John", 36)
```

```
print(p1.name)
print(p1.age)
```

The `__init__()` function is called automatically every time the class is being used to create a new object.

Object Methods

Objects can also contain methods. Methods in objects are functions that belong to the object.

Let us create a method in the `Person` class:

Example

Insert a function that prints a greeting, and execute it on the `p1` object:

```
class Person:
    def __init__(self, name, age):
        self.name = name
        self.age = age

    def myfunc(self):
        print("Hello my name is " + self.name)
```

```
p1 = Person("John", 36)
p1.myfunc()
```

The self Parameter

The `self` parameter is a reference to the current instance of the class, and is used to access variables that belongs to the class.

It does not have to be named `self`, you can call it whatever you like, but it has to be the first parameter of any function in the class:

Example

Use the words *mysillyobject* and *abc* instead of *self*:

```
class Person:
    def __init__(mysillyobject, name, age):
        mysillyobject.name = name
        mysillyobject.age = age
```

```
def myfunc(abc):
    print("Hello my name is " + abc.name)
```

```
p1 = Person("John", 36)
p1.myfunc()
```

Python Inheritance

Inheritance allows us to define a class that inherits all the methods and properties from another class.

Parent class is the class being inherited from, also called base class.

Child class is the class that inherits from another class, also called derived class.

Create a Parent Class

Any class can be a parent class, so the syntax is the same as creating any other class:

Example

Create a class named `Person`, with `firstname` and `lastname` properties, and a `printname` method:

```
class Person:
    def __init__(self, fname, lname):
        self.firstname = fname
```

```
self.lastname = lname

def printname(self):
    print(self.firstname, self.lastname)

#Use the Person class to create an object, and then execute the printname
method:

x = Person("John", "Doe")
x.printname()
```

Python Try Except

The **try** block lets you test a block of code for errors.

The **except** block lets you handle the error.

The **finally** block lets you execute code, regardless of the result of the try- and except blocks.

Exception Handling

When an error occurs, or exception as we call it, Python will normally stop and generate an error message.

These exceptions can be handled using the **try** statement:

Example

The **try** block will generate an exception, because **x** is not defined:

```
try:
    print(x)
except:
    print("An exception occurred")
```

Many Exceptions

You can define as many exception blocks as you want, e.g. if you want to execute a special block of code for a special kind of error:

Example

Print one message if the try block raises a `NameError` and another for other errors:

```
try:
    print(x)
except NameError:
    print("Variable x is not defined")
except:
    print("Something else went wrong")
```

Else

You can use the `else` keyword to define a block of code to be executed if no errors were raised:

Example

In this example, the `try` block does not generate any error:

```
try:
    print("Hello")
except:
    print("Something went wrong")
else:
    print("Nothing went wrong")
```

Finally

The `finally` block, if specified, will be executed regardless if the try block raises an error or not.

Example

```
try:
    print(x)
except:
    print("Something went wrong")
finally:
    print("The 'try except' is finished")
```